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A STUDY OF ATTITUDE OF TEACHERS TOWARDS - CAI PROGRAMMES FOR UNDERACHIEVERS

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ABSTRACT

The approach of school in general and teachers in particular is negatives towards underachievers. Underachievers are considered as a burden on school, and classroom and Indian schools are not yet equipped to meet their needs and solve their problems. If the class consists of some such children, the classroom discipline gets affected because of their unrest. Teachers are anxious, curious to attend their cognitive and emotional needs attended to reduce classroom disturbances. Technological interventions help overcome the underachievement in children. This is why interventions like CAI programmes are to be developed for extra tutorial, training of students based on their pace. Teachers understanding and attitude towards CAI plays a crucial role in use of CAI programmes at school. Present study attempts to know attitude of teachers towards one such study on use of CAI for underachievers. For this the investigators selected 30 teachers based on purposive sampling technique, who were part of the study on knowing impact of CAI. The sample was supplied questionnaire developed by investigators to measure attitude of teachers on different variables like gender, qualification (educational, professional), age, teaching experience and exposure to computers. Results and findings of this study on the one hand will help policy makers, educators to think of use of CAI programmes for students in Indian context and on the other hand help for developing strategies for teacher training and in-service programmes for using CAI programmes.

KEY TERMS: *Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) Programmes, Underachievers, attitude of teachers.*

INTRODUCTION

All the aspects of human life are witnessing impact of computers. Computers are being used in education since 1960, and the advent of micro computers in 1970s increased its usage in education. There are different uses of computers in education like for teaching, learning, data storage, administration, research and evaluation etc. The use of computers in teaching has lot of potential in the form use of computer assisted instruction in schools.

The need and significance of the study is evident from the following discourse. It is a common observation that the Urdu medium schools are ill-equipped as far as the academic and infrastructural facilities are concerned. The lack of qualified teachers and further lack of latest technologies and training of teachers in use of latest developments affects directly and indirectly on student community. This results in production of large number of underachievers. Hence, there is a need to fill this vacuum and the initiative can be taken up in the form of use of computer assisted instruction. Some of the teachers feel that the use of computers is interference, impediment in their work and computers try to replace classroom teacher, but this is actually not so in reality. The CAI programmes are just a supplementary effort and hence, teachers' attitude has to be ascertained, so that the needs of underachievers can be met.

Underachievement is a common concern, when the goal is for higher production or quality production. In common terms, if an individual or worker, who generally manufactures 100 items, consistently produces 30-40 items in few months, then this leads to underachievement. Underachievement is used in production, marketing, education etc. The underproduction or underachievement is concerned with states, nations, regions at large and individuals at gross root.

In education the underachievement is concerned with lower achievement of students in academics. The nation spends huge amount of public money for education of children and hence underachievement is a major concern at primary and secondary level.

- Underachievement is referred to as 'a student who does not perform as well as expected or as well as the I.Q. indicates'.
- Underachievement is the 'discrepancy between potential and performance, ability and achievement'.
- The underachievement among gifted students is a discrepancy between recognized ability and actual academic performance. The causes may be social, emotional, physical, and or academic, and they may originate at home or school.
- The underachievement is also known from
 -high IQ score and low achievement test score
 -high IQ score and low grades
 -high achievement test scores and low grades
 - high indication of intellectual creative potential and low creative productivity.
 -high indication of potential and limited presence of appropriate opportunity for intellectual and creative development.

The underachievement has become an issue of primary and secondary schools. Secondary school is the important step of the ladder for stepping into the higher education; negligence can create a problem of drop outs and low enrolment in higher education. Computers can help to overcome this problem of underachievement in absence of quality teachers. The CAI technique which is based on the individual and self paced learning will definitely become useful to the underachievers to improve their learning abilities.

Some of the characteristics which are given by (Silverman) were observed by the investigators in the children and they felt that the group of students whom teachers were teaching had following characteristics of gifted children. They were humorous, imaginative & Creative, Enquirer, had good memory and processed information, were sensitive, had expressiveness, reasoning, problem solving ability, relied on intuition, interest, motivated etc. At the same time their achievement in Science subject was quite below their general subjects.

The study involved all the teachers who were involved in the project intended to know the effectiveness of CAI on school children. The study involved government, private (aided) schools' boys, girls and hence, their respective teachers were part of the study. The study could be extended to Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh Urdu medium schools as the teachers were involved from both the states.

Some of the limitations of the study include that the study was limited to the teachers involved in the study, it was limited to only the science teachers, it had limitations in the form number of subject, geographic locations and also the study was limited to Urdu medium teachers only. The study limited itself to know the attitude of teachers of underachievers and not the underachievers towards CAI programmes.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Urdu school teachers like any other school teachers have enthusiasm for use of computers in schools for better training of students specially underachievers. Efforts were not made to know their attitude towards CAI as there is scarce or scanty research available. This has refrained the planners and policy makers away from planning CAI programmes for underachievers in Urdu medium. Hence, the investigators planned to make a study of attitude of Urdu medium teachers towards CAI programmes for underachievers in Karnataka and

Andhra Pradesh. The review of existing literature gave an idea that there were large number of studies available regarding knowing attitude of students towards use of computer and CAI, but very few or no studies were available to know the attitude of teachers towards use of CAI. Hence, present study is apparently a trend setting study in this regard.

The review of related literature has revealed that related studies can be classified in following categories.

Overall review indicates that computers are useful as a technology. The findings of Arkin (2003) imply that School of Foreign Languages (SFL) teachers are generally positive about computer technology use in language instruction and are willing to integrate computer technology resources into their teaching. Further, in the study conducted by Yushau (2006), it was found that the perception of the professor toward computer is more of a positive tool that can enhance teaching and learning process. Some difficult subjects like computers can also be taught through use of computers and Yushau, 2006 has quoted from the study of Kadijevich, 2002 as “Mathematics professors at KFUPM have positive attitudes toward computers and towards the use of computers in their academic activities. This is encouraging as it has been realized that computer attitudes influence not only the acceptance of computers, but also their use as professional tools or as teaching/learning aids”. Therefore, to have computers widely used in mathematics classrooms, we should first help teachers develop positive attitudes toward the machine.(Yushau, 2006) Hence, there is a need to know attitude of different stakeholders towards computers in different settings.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERMS USED IN THE STUDY

Attitude towards CAI

This is a predisposition or tendency of Urdu medium teachers to respond positively or negatively towards use of computer assisted instruction in schools.

Urdu Medium Teachers

The high school teachers who are teaching science subject in Urdu medium schools.

Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI)

This is content based, self-learning, structured, offline computer programme, involving teaching in a programmed instructional format. This uses a combination of text, graphics, sound and video in enhancing learning.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To compare the attitude of teachers based on gender towards CAI programmes for underachievers.
- To determine the attitude of teachers based on academic qualification towards CAI programmes for underachievers.
- To compare the attitude of teachers based on professional qualification towards CAI programmes for underachievers.
- To compare the attitude of teachers based on average age towards CAI programmes for underachievers.
- To establish a relationship of the attitude of teachers based on teaching experience towards CAI programmes for underachievers.
- To contrast the attitude of teachers based on exposure of computers towards CAI programmes for underachievers.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- H₀: There is no significant difference in the attitudes of teachers based on gender towards CAI programmes.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on academic qualification towards CAI programmes.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on professional qualification towards CAI programmes.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on average age towards CAI programmes.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on teaching experience towards CAI programmes.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on exposure of computers towards CAI programmes.

METHODOLOGY

Survey technique as described in Best (1989) and Koul (1984) was adopted for knowing the attitude of teachers towards use of CAI. Best (1989) says survey requires expert and imaginative planning, careful analysis and interpretation of the data gathered, and logical and careful reporting of the findings. Present study was part of the experimental study conducted to know impact of CAI programmes. All the teachers were part of the study and had good knowledge of CAI methodology.

A sample of 30 secondary school teachers from two districts each of Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh were part of the UGC-MRP study for knowing 'Impact of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) on Underachievers in Science at Selected Urdu Medium Secondary Schools of Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh'. The sample was selected by using systematic purposive sampling technique. Since only 30 teachers were involved in the study the entire universe or population was accommodated to know the attitude of teachers.

The variables of the study include gender, qualification (both academic and professional), age, experience and exposure to computer teachers' as independent and their attitude towards CAI programme as dependent variable.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOLS USED

The investigators developed a five-point attitude scale in the form of opinionnaire consisting of 35 items. The items were arranged from strongly agree to strongly disagree and corresponding scores ranged from 4 to 0 respectively for each of the item. Theoretically maximum of 140 and minimum of 0 score could be obtained by an individual for 35 items. The tools was designed to know teachers attitude towards CAI with respect to knowing effectiveness of content, pictures, format, attainment of objectives, students' response, need for more programmes, development of such supplementary materials, enhancement of learning in students, speed of learning etc.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

For the analysis of data, the investigators referred Garrett (1986), and used simple statistical techniques such as Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test and ANOVA. The calculations were made using data analysis from MS Excel.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The opinions of the responding teachers were collected, tabulated, classified and the data thus analysed is presented below to test hypothesis.

To test the hypotheses (H1-H3), the data of was subjected to t-test. The scores were obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 1.

Table 1 t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances of Gender (male & female), educational qualification (Bachelor & Masters) and professional qualification (Bachelor & Masters)

Variables		Mean	Variance	Observations	Pooled Variance	HMD#	df	t Stat	P(T<=t) two-tail	t Critical two-tail
Gender	Male	62.63	29.7	8	120.98	0	28	-0.8*	0.41	2.05
	Female	66.45	151.4	22						
Academic Qualification	Bachelor	63.45	81	20	115.62	0	28	-1.4*	0.16	2.05
	Master	69.4	188.71	10						
Professional Qualification	Bachelor	66.04	124.04	27	120.53	0	28	0.9*	0.37	2.05
	Master	60	75	3						

#HMD- Hypothesized Mean Difference, * not significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 1 indicates that the t Stat for male and female is 0.8 for $P(T \leq t)$ (one-tail) at 0.41; t-stat for Bachelor and Master degree academic qualification is 1.4 for $P(T \leq t)$ (two-tail) at 0.16 and t-stat for Bachelor and Master degree professional qualification is 1.2 for $P(T \leq t)$ (two-tail) at 0.9 are all less than the t Critical two-tail values. Hence, the null hypotheses H1, H2, H3 are accepted. The same attitude of teachers belonging to male, female groups indicate that people belonging to different gender do not have different preferences towards the use of CAI. The impact of academic qualification on attitude is negligible, this means that the bachelor and master degree holders have similar feeling towards use of computers. There is no evidence of impact of higher professional qualification on attitude of respondents. Hence, it is felt that irrespective of gender, qualifications (academic, profession) teachers like to use CAI programmes for improving achievement of students of high schools in science subject. The teachers have similar background i.e. science background hence, there attitude towards programme may be similar. However, by changing the background of teachers to arts, crafts or other subjects comparison can be drawn up.

To test the hypothesis H4, the data of was subjected to ANOVA test. The scores were obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 2.

Table 2 Anova: Single Factor of teachers based on different age groups regarding their opinion towards effectiveness of CAI

SUMMARY

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
20-30 years	12	871	72.58	177.54
30-40 years	10	610	61.00	45.11
40-50 years	8	482	60.25	12.79

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1024.95	2	512.47	5.65**	0.01	3.35
Within Groups	2448.42	27	90.68			
Total	3473.37	29				

** Significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 2 indicates that the calculated F-value is 5.65 for P value of 0.01, which is more than F Crit value of 3.35. Therefore, the null hypothesis H4 is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the opinions of the teachers based on

different age groups (20-30, 30-40, 40-50 years) regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme. That is the teachers with three different age groups (20-30,30-40, 40-50 years) possessed different opinions regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.

Therefore, further analysis was required to determine difference between these three different groups. Hence, the data was subjected to further analysis using t-test, by using two groups at a time. The analyses are given in the table below.

Table 3 t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances of different age groups (20-30, 30-40; 20-30, 40-50; 30-40, 40-50 years)

	Mea n	Varianc e	Observation s	Pooled Varianc e	HMD #	df	t Stat	P(T<=t) two- tail	t Critical two-tail
20-30 year s	72.5 8	177.54	12	118	0	2 0	2.49* *	0.02	2.09
30-40 year s	61	45.11	10						
20-30 year s	72.5 8	177.54	12	113.5	0	1 8	2.54* *	0.02	2.1
40-50 year s	60.3	12.8	8						
30-40 year s	61	45.11	10	30.97	0	1 6	0.28*	0.78	2.12
40-50 year s	60.3	12.8	8						

#HMD- Hypothesized Mean Difference,* not significant at 0.05 level, ** significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 3 indicates that the t Stat for 20-30 years and 30-40 years of age groups is 2.49 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.02 (more than t Critical two-tail); t-stat for 20-30 years and 40-50 years is 2.54 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.02 (more than t Critical two-tail) and t-stat for 30-40 years and 40-50 years of age is 0.28 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.78 (less than t Critical two-tail). Hence, it is concluded that 20-30 years age group respondents differ in their attitude towards CAI with that of the 30-40, and 40-50 years of age, and the mean score tilts in favour youngest age group in both the case as they have more positive attitude than those with more

1998. The younger group is making use of computers for more time and aware of its usage in education and this may be having an impact on their having positive attitude towards CAI programmes. However, there is no significant difference in the other two senior groups. This may be because as the teacher grow in age they get accustomed to traditional methodology and doesn't find any scope of use of computers. They rely more on their teaching them on CAI and hence, the attitude in this group is similar.

To test the hypothesis (H5), having data from 4 variables groups the data of was subjected to ANOVA test. The scores of respondents based on years of teaching experience was obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 4.

Table 4 Anova: Single Factor of teachers based on years of teaching experience regarding their opinion towards effectiveness of CAI

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
7 years or less	14	965	68.93	190.84
07-15 years	10	638	63.80	64.40
15-25 years	4	234	58.50	3.67
above 25 years	2	126	63.00	0.00

ANOVA

<i>Source Variation</i>	<i>of SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	401.84	3	133.95	1.13*	0.35	2.98
Within Groups	3071.53	26	118.14			
Total	3473.37	29				

* not significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 4 indicates that the calculated F-value is 1.13 for P value of 0.35, which is less than F Crit value of 2.98. Therefore, the null hypothesis H5 is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the attitudes of the teachers based on years of teaching (7 years or less, 07-15 years, 15-25 years) regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme. That is the teachers from four groups with different years of teaching experience (7 years or less, 07-15 years, 15-25 years, above 25 years) possessed similar attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction

programme. The teachers of younger age have more positive attitude towards computers as evident in analysis of H4, but the teachers with lesser experience have same attitude of higher experience teachers here. This may be because the number of years of teaching do not correspond to age of the teachers. E.g. a teacher with 35 years of age may be entrant and less than 7 years of teaching or a teacher with the same age may also be part of group having teaching experience in the group of 15-25 years. Hence, age and teaching experience can not be correlated.

To test hypothesis (H6), the data of was subjected to t-test. The scores of teachers with slight exposure and those who had rigorous training of computers were obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 5.

Table 5 t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances of computer experience of teachers regarding their opinion towards effectiveness of CAI

	<i>slight exposure</i>	<i>rigorous training</i>
Mean	65.88	63.20
Variance	117.03	158.70
Observations	25	5
Pooled Variance	122.98	
Hypothesized Difference	Mean	0
df	28	
t Stat	0.49*	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.63	
t Critical two-tail	2.05	

* not significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 5 indicates that the t Stat is 0.49 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.63 which is less than t Critical two-tail value of 2.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H6) is accepted and there is no significant difference between the teachers having slight exposure or rigorous training with regard to their attitude towards CAI. Irrespective of exposure to computers all teachers feel equally about the use of CAI, this may be because of they equally envisage the potential usage of computers in schools.

Findings of the study

- The male and female teachers possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.

- The teachers with bachelor or masters degree educational qualification possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers with bachelor or masters degree professional qualification possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers with three different age groups (20-30,30-40, 40-50 years) possessed different attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers with 20-30 years age and 30-40 years of age possessed different attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers with 20-30 years age and 40-50 years of age possessed different attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers with 30-40 years age and 40-50 years of age possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers grouped in four categories with different years of teaching experience (7 years or less, 07-15 years, 15-25 years, above 25 years) possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.
- The teachers having slight exposure and rigorous training of computers possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme for underachievers.

The findings of the present study are in line with those of the findings of TILFARLIOĞLU and UNALDI (2006). The results revealed that faculty attitudes towards computer assisted instruction are positive. Age, sex, teaching experience, level of proficiency in English and computer usage skills have no or little effects over these attitudes.

SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The study was limited to the teachers involved in the UGC-MRP project undertaken by the investigators. It may be extended beyond this limited group. The study may be undertaken by involving primary, higher primary; government, private; rural, urban; different mediums of teachers etc. The teachers may be encouraged to develop and test their own software. The study may be extended by taking opinion of the students who were really underachievers regarding CAI programmes.

CONCLUSION

The computer assisted instruction programmes are very systematic, organised, interesting form of instruction. These programmes due to contemporary content and use of multi-media potentialities have very good potential for education of children specifically underachieving children. We cannot think of programmes without the help of teachers, where as these programmes can be supplementary to the classroom teaching. The gifted students who are underperforming in linguistic minority schools specially Urdu medium schools may be given opportunity for more inputs through computers. The enthusiasm of the teachers may be used for the benefit of student learning.

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